

EVALUATION OF STUDENTS' KNOWLEDGE OF THEORETICAL MECHANICS USING A NEW METHOD

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Abstract: Using the method of the interactive confused logical chain, the problem of a fair determination of students' knowledge level and increase of their activity in classes was considered. It is shown that by using this method for one topic, section, and whole part of theoretical mechanics, it is possible to evaluate the level of students' knowledge fairly, transparently, and quickly.

Keywords: *theoretical mechanics, statics, frictional force, frictional cone, sliding frictional force, rolling frictional force, Poinso's lemma, equilibrium equation, oscillatory motion, theorem, moment of inertia.*

Great positive changes are being made in the field of education in our country. The number of students in higher educational institutions and the number of educational fields is constantly expanding and increasing, the financial resources allocated to education are increasing, educational institutions are being overhauled and new ones are being built. The task of improving the quality of education is assigned to professors and teachers of the institute. The increase in the number of students requires the provision of quality education and the use of fair, quick, and transparent methods of assessing the level of education. The issue of applying the confused logical chain method, which has been widely used in higher educational institutions recently, in theoretical mechanics training is considered urgent.

One of the interactive pedagogical methods, the "entangled logical chain" method is used as one of the most effective methods for determining the level of

students' knowledge of theoretical mechanics. It is possible to use this method within the framework of a subject of theoretical mechanics, in the process of conducting an intermediate assessment, and in the stage of conducting a final assessment. When this method is used, the student should be able to match the correct ones among them when the information on several studied topics are confused together, such as formulas, keywords and phrases, definitions, and theorems related to science. In this case, the collection of facts related to the topic is presented to the attention of students in a case where the chronological order of cause and effect is confused (broken). Students should be able to correctly place the assigned task in order.

Let's see the application of the method in the teaching process of the topic "Friction force" of the statics section of theoretical mechanics. Based on the method of the confused logical chain, information is presented in the form of expressions, quantities, and formulas on the subject. The teacher distributes a copy of the table to the group of students, corresponding to the number of students in the audience. After studying the given table in detail, the students of the group write down the answer number for each question listed on the left and the corresponding number on the right. The teacher collects the answers from all students, checks them, and announces the results. Below is a chart on the topic of friction force.

Determine compatibility:

1	Show the formula for calculating the friction force in rolling	1	$F_{ish} = f \cdot N$
2	What is the direction of the frictional force in sliding?	2	$\vec{R} = \vec{N} + \vec{F}_{ish}$

3	What is the total reaction force?	3	always opposed to action
4	What is a friction cone?	4	the formula for calculating the friction force is added to the series of balance equations
5	Show the formula for calculating the frictional force in sliding	5	$F_{\text{ish}} = \frac{\delta}{R} \cdot N$
6	How to solve the problem by taking into account the force of friction	6	a figure drawing in space the force of friction and the normal reaction force are equal to each other

Correct answers (5,3,2,6,1,4).

Let's use the fuzzy logic chain method for statics, a branch of theoretical mechanics. The results obtained from this score can be used to test student's knowledge in a non-traditional way to quickly determine the level of mastery of the studied section by the student or to determine intermediate assessment scores. The number of questions in the table is more than the assessment of one subject. Because the greater the number of questions, the higher the level of impartiality and fairness. At the beginning of each academic year, professors and teachers of the department form a bank of questions on subjects, and they are regularly filled and improved. Below is the table covering all the topics of Statics of Theoretical Mechanics:

Determine compatibility:

1	State Poinceau's lemma	1	in order to treat a non-free body as free, the bonds must be replaced by the bond reaction force
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2	When is the moment of force about the axis equal to zero	2	a problem in which the number of unknowns in a given problem is equal to or less than the equilibrium equations
3	The amount of the couple force is equal to 10 n, the force shoulder is equal to 2 m. Find the torque.	3	$22 n$
4	State the conditions of analytical equilibrium of a system of forces meeting in a plane	4	$\sum F_{kx} = 0$, $\sum F_{ky} = 0$, $\sum m_o(\vec{F}_k) = 0$
5	Show the formula for finding the radius vector of the center of parallel forces	5	$x_c = \frac{\sum l_k \cdot x_k}{\sum l_k} \quad , \quad y_c = \frac{\sum l_k \cdot y_k}{\sum l_k} \quad ,$ $z_c = \frac{\sum l_k \cdot z_k}{\sum l_k}$
6	State the unbinding axiom	6	when the force acting on the body is moved parallel to itself, the force equal to the force at the point of displacement and the added double product
7	Show the conditions of analytical equilibrium of a system of forces located in a plane	7	$\sum F_{kx} = 0$, $\sum F_{ky} = 0$
8	What is the direction of the moment vector of the force relative to the	8	force modulus is obtained by multiplying the force shoulder with the appropriate sign

	axis		
9	Show the definition of moment of force about a point	9	along the axis, when this vector is viewed from three sides, the force rotates the body counterclockwise
10	What kind of problem is called a static definite problem	10	when the force and axis lie in the same plane
11	A 22 n mass is suspended from a rope hanging from the ceiling. Find the tension in the rope	11	20 nm
12	Show the formula for finding the coordinates of the center of gravity of a line	12	$\vec{r}_c = \frac{\sum \vec{F}_k \cdot \vec{r}_k}{\sum \vec{F}_k}$

Correct answers (6,10,11,7,12,1,4,9,8,2,3,5).

As a result of using the studied method to determine the level of knowledge acquired by students in the entire field of theoretical mechanics, it is possible to quickly, transparently and fairly evaluate their level of knowledge. In this case, the teacher selects materials from the question bank from the departments of statics, kinematics and dynamics of science. The table covering all the sections of the subject is given below. It is natural that the number of questions offered to students increases with the increase in the weight of the material. However, after a certain number of questions (25-30), using the fuzzy logic chain method causes a number of inconveniences. For this reason, it is recommended to use this method

without increasing the number of questions from 20 to 25 when conducting the final evaluation of the subject.

Determine compatibility:

1	Show the differential equation of motion of free oscillations	1	$m\ddot{x} + 2b\dot{x} + k^2x = 0$
2	State the conditions of analytical equilibrium of a system of forces meeting in space	2	$\vec{R} = \sum \vec{F}_k = 0, \vec{M}_0 = \sum \vec{m}_0(\vec{F}_k) = 0$
3	Show the theorem about the change of momentum of a material point	3	The point of intersection of the vertical lines transferred to the velocities is the instantaneous center of the velocities
4	What formula is used to find the work done by the force of friction?	4	$J_{oc^1} = J_{Cz} + md^2$
5	Give an example of complex motion of a point	5	given the mass of the body and the law of motion, the acting force is found
6	State the axiom of reaction to action	6	A light bulb hanging from the ceiling, a teapot on the table
7	Find the trajectory of a material point moving in the plane according to the law $x=5\cos 20t-4$ m, $y=3\sin 20t+2$ m	7	$\vec{a}_{ab} = \vec{a}_r + \vec{a}_e + \vec{a}_{kor}$
8	What is the first question of dynamics	8	Man in Motion wristwatch hand movement

9	How to find the equation of trajectory when the point law of motion is given in a plane	9	a force that alone can show the effect of a system of forces on a body
10	Show the formula for circular motion with uniform acceleration	10	smooth circular motion
11	State the conditions of geometric equilibrium of a system of forces with an arbitrary location in space	11	$\sum F_{kx} = 0$, $\sum F_{ky} = 0$, $\sum F_{kz} = 0$
12	Show the differential equation of damped oscillatory motion	12	$\ddot{x} + k^2 x = 0$
13	How to find the instantaneous center of velocities if the directions of the velocities of two points of a flat shape are known	13	The change in the amount of motion of a material point in a finite period of time is equal to the impulse of the force acting on the point
14	Give an example of a body in a bond	14	The effects of two bodies on each other are equal in amount and opposite in direction
15	Show the formula of Huygens Steiner's theorem	15	$A(F_{ish}) = -f \cdot N \cdot s$
16	An equal acting force is a	16	time is clearly lost from the given equation of motion
17	What kind of rotary	17	$\varphi = \varphi_0 + \omega_0 \cdot t + \frac{\varepsilon \cdot t^2}{2}$

7	motion is the movement of the clock shaft?		
18	Show the expression of the theorem of addition of accelerations in the complex motion of a point	18	$\frac{(x + 4)^2}{25} + \frac{(y - 2)^2}{9} = 1$, эллипс

Correct answers (12,11,13,15,8,14,18,5,16,17,2,1,3,6,4,9,10,7).

In short, as a result of using the method of the confused logical chain, students develop knowledge and skills such as organizing the subjects they have studied in science, dividing them into components, comparing them with other parts of the subject, and understanding information about the newly studied subject. Regular use of this method in lectures allows students to systematically study science materials, and organize, divide, and differentiate what they have learned. As a result of the above facts, the level of knowledge of students will increase significantly. The activity of students in the lessons also increases. The teacher will have the opportunity to objectively determine the level of students' knowledge quickly, and to conduct intermediate and final evaluations successfully.

When it is planned to evaluate students' knowledge using the method of confused logical chain by the teacher-teacher, the following should be paid attention to:

- the bank of science questions should be expanded and compiled by topic.
- a bank of questions should be prepared separately for each subject, chapter, and part of the subject.
- it is necessary to create a bank of logical, relatively easy-to-solve examples and problems related to the topics.

- to determine the level of mastery of the subject of science, table options of 5-10 questions are compiled, at least equal to the number of students in the group.

- to evaluate students' knowledge in mid-term control, the professor-teacher offers them the option of tables consisting of 10-20 questions.

- it is recommended to prepare tables of 15-25 questions for the final control evaluation of the subject.

- Samples of the question bank and example-problem bank and the order of execution are regularly published on the website of the department.

- the bank of questions and the bank of examples are updated every academic year.

So, the method of the confused logical chain is one of the modern and convenient methods for determining the level of students' knowledge. This method is distinguished from other evaluation methods by the fact that it is especially effective in checking the knowledge of students on one topic of science, on one chapter of science, and during midterm control.

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